

INVENTORY APPROACH FOR DETERIORATING ITEMS WITH DEMAND DEPENDENT RATE UNDER PERMISSIBLE DELAY IN PAYMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The author has considered inventory approach for deteriorating items analyzed by the study of the researchers. Inventory, control for damageable items as a type of deteriorating items as electric bulb, glass and ceramic items etc. Thus these items put the retailer of breakable items in a conflicting situation between large and small size of order to minimize sum of cost of ordering shortage and damageable of stocks. Due to breakable number of items it is delicious change for wholesalers and retailers. Dependency between damaging rate and inventor level.

Keywords: Inventory management, demand rate economic order, production.

INTRODUCTION

The inventory models management for deteriorating items an emerging and important field for production and supply chain management. Inventory control model for breakable item with shortage is allocated which damaging rate is exponential and unsatisfied items will completely. The inventory management for deteriorating items is one of the most powerful tools of production and sales producers. Inventory approach for breakable items is a system of deteriorating items. Literature shows that researchers have given lot of attention in recent years to inventory lot-sizing models with deterioration. An approach was suggested by Silver and meal to find out the solution for general case of a deterministic and time varying demand pattern.

MATHEMATICAL SOLUTION

The behavior system of deteriorating items can be defined at any time by derivatives which are as follows:

$$\frac{\delta I(t)}{\delta t} = -\Delta(t) - QI(t), 0 \leq t \leq t_1$$

$$\frac{\delta I(t)}{\delta t} = -\Delta(t) - t_1 \leq t \leq T$$

$$I(t) = \alpha(t_1 - T) + \frac{\beta}{2}(t_1^2 - T^2), t_1 \leq t \leq t_1$$

$$S = I(0) = \left(\frac{\alpha}{Q} - \frac{\beta}{Q^2}\right) (e^{\theta t_1} - 1) + \frac{\beta}{\theta} t_1 e^{\theta t_1}$$

$$\Delta r = S - \int_0^{t_1} \Delta(t) \delta t = s - \int_0^{t_1} (\alpha + \beta t) \delta t$$

$$\Delta r = \left(\frac{\alpha}{Q} - \frac{\beta}{Q^2}\right) (e^{\theta t_1} - 1) - 1 + \frac{\beta}{Q} t_1 e^{\theta t_1} - \alpha t_1 - \frac{1}{2} \beta t_1^2$$

$$J_t = \left(\frac{\alpha + \beta t_1}{Q^2} - \frac{\beta}{Q^3}\right) (e^{\theta t_1} - 1) - \frac{\alpha Q - \beta}{Q^2} t_1 - \frac{\beta}{2Q} t_1^2$$

For the interval $[t_1, T]$ above equation can be expressed as:

$$J'_t = -\int_{t_1}^T \left[\alpha(t_1 - t) + \frac{\beta}{2}(t_1^2 - t^2) \right] \delta t$$

$$= \frac{\alpha}{2} \left[T^2 + \frac{3}{2} t_1^2 - 2t_1 T \right] + \frac{\beta}{6} \left[T^3 + 2t_1^3 - 3t_1^2 T \right]$$

$$c_1(t_1) = \frac{1}{T} \left[A_0 + C_1 \Delta r + c_2 J_T + c_3 J'_T \right]$$

Therefore
$$\left[\left(c_1 + \frac{c_2}{Q} \right) (e^{\theta t_1} - 1) + c_3 (t_1 - T) \right] (\alpha + \beta t_1) = 0$$

This equation represents that is a monotonic increasing function for $e^{\theta T} > 1$ and has a unique solution.

Average shortage inventory model:

The average shortage inventory during t_1 can be given as:

$$AS = \frac{0 + X}{2} = \frac{X}{2}$$

Here, $t_1 = \frac{X}{\Delta}$, hence the shortage cost for interval of time t_1 can be given by the shortage cost

$$= \frac{SX t_1}{2} = \frac{SX^2}{2\Delta}$$

$$Q t_2 = \Delta t_1 + \Delta t_2 \text{ and } t_2 = \frac{X}{Q - \Delta}$$

The shortage cost during time interval t_1+t_2 is given by

$$SC = \frac{SX^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{\Delta} + \frac{1}{\theta - \Delta} \right] = \frac{SX^2}{2} \left[\frac{\theta - \Delta + \Delta}{\Delta(\theta - \Delta)} \right] = \frac{SX^2\theta}{2\Delta(\theta - \Delta)}$$

The positive inventory occurs during time interval $T - (t_1+t_2)$, where $T - t_1+t_2+t_3+t_4$ and hence, the average inventory for the time interval t_3+t_4 varies between a minimum and zero and a minimum of $(Q-\Delta)t_3$ stage, and the production during the time interval

$$t_2+t_3 = \frac{P}{Q} \Rightarrow t_3 = \frac{P}{Q} - t_2$$

$$t_2 = \frac{X}{Q-D} \quad \text{and} \quad t_3 = \frac{P}{Q} - \frac{X}{Q-D}$$

$$t_3 = \frac{P(Q-\Delta) - XQ}{Q(Q-\Delta)}$$

$$H(Q-\Delta) \left\{ \frac{P(Q-\Delta) - XQ}{2Q(Q-\Delta)} \right\} \left\{ \frac{P(Q-\Delta) - XQ}{\Delta(Q-\Delta)} \right\} = \frac{H[P(Q-\Delta) - XQ]^2}{2Q\Delta(Q-\Delta)}$$

$$TC(P, X) = CP + K \frac{H[P(Q-\Delta) - XQ]}{2Q\Delta(Q-\Delta)} + \frac{SX^2Q}{2\Delta(Q-\Delta)}$$

$$TC \cup (P, X) = CP + \frac{K\Delta}{P} + \frac{H[P(Q-\Delta) - XP]}{2PQ(Q-\Delta)} + \frac{SX^2Q}{2P(Q-\Delta)}$$

In which
$$P = \sqrt{\frac{H+S}{H}} \cdot \frac{XQ}{Q-\Delta} + \sqrt{\frac{2K\Delta Q}{H(Q-\Delta)}}$$

Then
$$TC \cup (P, X) = C\Delta + \frac{K\Delta}{Q^+} + \frac{H[Q^+(Q-\Delta)]}{2Q^+Q(Q-\Delta)} + \frac{SX^2Q}{2P(Q-\Delta)}$$

The system operates at time $t=0$ at a demand rate Δ upto time $t=t_1$ to allow shortage of X units to occur. Then production starts where the inventory level increases at a rate $(Q-\Delta)$ in order to satisfy the demand and to eliminate the rate of level defines continuously at a demand rate Δ and becomes zero at time $t_1+t_2+t_3+t_4$. Now the cost's components consists of shortage.

Analyze for economic production quantity

$$Q^+ = \sqrt{\frac{H+S}{S}} + \sqrt{\frac{2K\Delta Q}{H(Q-\Delta)}}$$

$$Q^+ = \sqrt{\frac{0.75+2}{2}} + \sqrt{\frac{2 \times 230 \times 61500.178400}{0.75(178400-61500)}}$$

$$Q^+ = \sqrt{1.375} + \sqrt{\frac{5.652.10^{12}}{0.75(116900)}}$$

Therefore a stationery point to be an extreme point the matrix of partial derivatives upto second order and this model in which we the review has been done for the importance of inventory cost minimization in order to increase the profitability.

Forecasting model for economic order quantity:

The forecast quantity is decided by a specific time duration called as forecast period. The recorder point forecasting is very-very important for wholesale business because this deals with higher quantities of stock and capital. It is level of inventory which triggers an action to replenish that certain stock. An EOQ in a key part of the fore casting process. Through this work EOQ decide on the ideal order quantity that minimizes inventory costs while matching customer demand where

$$ECQ = \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta K}{H}} \text{ in which } \Delta \text{ be the fixed cost per year}$$

K be the demand in units per year and

H be the carrying cost per unit year.

Statistical Fore Casting Demand using EOQ :

The statistical forecast demand is done using methodoloty moving average and date mining techniques i.e. lines regression and back propagation. This statistical technique is mostly used for forecasting demands in the retail manufacturing plants. It is an ineffective forecasting technique it does not take variability in consideration and there is no application of economic order quantity application.

This technique is used for forecast demand. It considers quarters, unit sales to predict demand. EOQ models are applied to determine optimal order quantity for selected product.

Forecast	Unit price cost	Holding cost	Lead time	Fixed order costs	EOQ	Cycle time	Total quarter cost
204.8	267	0.24	7	181.1	33.3	15	2221.16

Model of behavior of Inventory System at any time:

The shortage the backlogging rates are variable and are depends on the length of the waiting time for the next replenishment. The backlogging rate will be smaller for longer waiting times. Hence the fraction of customers who likes to accept backlogging at time t decreases with the waiting time $(T - t)$ for the next replenishment. The replenishment policy of the deteriorating item with partial backlogging is considered.

CONCLUSION

A predetermined constant rate of demand with no any effect on shortages has been assumed by classical order quantity model. It has also been shown that together with the demand the costs also varies with time and both are affected by shortages. The general inferences are limited by the use of actual items data in inventory simulations systems. It has been observed that the economic quantity model gives the best performance in purchase of cost low values. The number of items is the base and is mostly recommended in order to reduce the process inventory. The inventory average results were practically the same of the up to order level and higher than the requirements planning.

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